

POLITICAL SCIENCES

SPECIFICS OF HUMAN NATURE AND STRONG FACTORS IN COUNTERING CORRUPTION

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Abstract

Today corruption among those in power is traditionally seen as a legal, sociocultural or economic problem. However, Russian and foreign social science literature has no works revealing its natural roots. Such a view of the fundamentals of corruption is still considered to be contrary to the idea of a social nature of a person. Meanwhile, nearly 2,500 years ago, Aristotle clearly called the sapiens “a political animal”, emphasizing that human nature is integral to building people’s life together. That is why, in the author’s opinion, a group of hierarchical tendencies, inherited from hominid ancestors and developed historically in every possible way, is, in particular, preserved in the man’s species nature. It also invites human individuals to self-serving manipulation of power and people’s subordination in order to build “food chains” between them and gain vital resources and benefits kleptocratically. Thus, the governance of society and building order therein based on corrupt methods erases the seemingly unshakable sociocultural borderline between a man and his animal ancestors. The article emphasizes that corruption exists not only because of imperfection of, relic and predatory components of human nature, but, most importantly, because of legal, ethical and economic reasons. But the state anti-corruption policy should also consider the natural qualities of a human being.

Keywords: hierarchy, power, innate behavior programs, official powers, administrative markup.

There are fewer and fewer people today who disagree with the fact that there is a social pandemic of corruption in the modern world, partly covert, partly in broad daylight [15, p. 29]. It causes great damage, and sometimes deals a devastating blow to improving the quality of life of the majority of the population of developed, developing and underdeveloped countries of the planet. As indicated by Christine Lagarde, former director of the International Monetary Fund, the annual volume of bribes in the world reaches USD 2 trillion. Through sophisticated corruption techniques, they vanish from public funds primarily into the pockets of officials. Moreover, she says that these nearly 2% of the world’s GDP are just the tip of the iceberg, since the level of global corruption is greatly increased due to the scale of criminal tax evasion, money laundering and many other corruption crimes. The latter directly or indirectly generate further increasing volumes of corruption in the world¹. At the same time, despite the numerous states’ and people’s efforts at the global and regional levels to curb, first of all, abuses of public authority for personal gain, these attempts have so far had little impact on the escalation of this global disaster. And they cannot stop the growth of a variety of forms and types of corrupt practices in the world [17, p. 71-118].

This situation with confronting the corruption pandemic makes me wonder about this. Fight against this scourge was first mentioned in the 24th century BC and coincided with the decay of primitive tribal communities and the development of the states of the Ancient

World. According to cuneiform texts, after his election, Urukagina, the ruler of the city-state Lagash, (2318-2311 BC) carried out some reforms to curb the royal official malpractices. He forbade them to willfully collect the population’s income from fishing and cattle breeding for their own benefit, reduced charges and duties on temple people, and reduced and streamlined payments for various religious rites [12, p. 199]. Arthashastra, the ancient Indian treatise on statecraft (IV-III centuries BC), also recommends the ruler to control not only ordinary people, but also closely monitor all superiors. The measure is necessary to identify those who are dissatisfied with his policies and traitors, and, on top of that, to cut off dozens of practices and methods used by government officials to “bite off at least some of the royal income” [4, p. 31-37, 284-299].

Thus, for more than 4 millennia (!) mankind has not only failed to defeat corruption, but even to keep it within any acceptable levels. Meanwhile, people were able to cope, for example, with the threats of global mass hunger, significantly reduce today’s wars and violence in international relations, child mortality and acute poverty, and eliminate plague, smallpox, typhoid and other epidemics. It has even been possible to achieve the fundamental, albeit declarative so far, equality of all people on the planet, but corruption as a public disaster happened to be akin to large-scale droughts, floods and other climatic disturbances, and modern societies cannot manage to root it out yet. So maybe it really is inherent in the deep human nature and

¹ Annual volume of bribes in the world reaches two trillion dollars // Novye Izvestia. September 18, 2017. URL: <https://newizv.ru/news/economy/18-09-2017/ezhegodnyy->

[ob-yom-vzyatok-v-mire-dostigaet-dvuh-trillionov-dollarov](https://newizv.ru/news/economy/18-09-2017/ezhegodnyy-ob-yom-vzyatok-v-mire-dostigaet-dvuh-trillionov-dollarov) (access date: July 27, 2019).

therefore not subject to any public measures to eliminate it?!

Indeed, despite the largest variety of cultures, peoples and local civilizations in the history of mankind, their current diversity, their corruption crimes and offenses are very similar and may be said to be typical for our species. Bribes, embezzlement of public funds, abuse of power, misappropriation and embezzlement of common property resources, fraud, nepotism, favoritism, self-serving use of a conflict of interest, abuse of administrative influence and the right to trial - these illegal and criminal manipulations of power entrusted to persons in charge are literally carbon-copied in administrative and criminal codes of various countries and peoples. At the same time, it is very important that the typical nature of such offenses and crimes allowed the world community to embark upon the development of common international anti-corruption laws from the end of the 20th century, at the beginning of the 21st century. The UN Convention against Corruption (2003), today acceded to by 172 countries worldwide, the Global Programme against Corruption, the European Declarations on Prosecution of and Civil Liability for Corruption have been agreed. Moreover, relying on their common interests, states and the international community organized such anti-corruption institutions as Transparency International, GRECO, other European, African and Latin American anti-corruption associations and groups.

On top of that, the unavoidable natural roots of corrupt behavior by officials suggest those characteristic and symptomatic passions - compulsiveness and frenzy touching on personality disorder, with which an endless number of bureaucrats, politicians and administrators seek to convert their power into their own benefits and profits. At the same time, such an obsession acquires the nature of a fixed idea that encourages them to engage in shady ventures despite the often obvious threats to deal a crippling blow to their lives and fate, and to their loved ones. And the most striking is to plunge into criminal fraud, despite the inability to sometimes use the stolen and misappropriated goods personally, in everyday life and for their intended purpose. An example of Aleksandr Menshikov, an associate of Peter the Great of humble origin, who seized six Russian cities and financial assets that exceeded the annual budget of the Russian Empire, can tell us something about a similar inhuman obsession [11, p. 77].

It is also necessary to challenge the coincidence of typical methods of misappropriation of someone else's goods by human individuals - with the characteristic methods of taking over and embezzlement of various resources and values in primate populations, and in many other communities of relatively developed animals. After all, a man, like his relatives in nature, just as often uses the hierarchy of individuals' subordination in his community, that is, the emerging relations of power and obedience between people, not only to manage and establish a general order, but also for his own

good, for own survival and selfish prosperity. No wonder that neurobiologists conducting a comparative analysis of animals' and humans' drives often emphasize that "hierarchy is a system of subordination that establishes unequal access to limited resources, from meat to a vague notion called "prestige"... Hierarchies establish the status quo by ritualizing inequality ... The hierarchical system protects personal gain. Behavioral acts proclaiming the status quo clearly help the top." [19, p. 381-382]

Numerous social research results, as well as historical evidence characterizing corruption as a natural, pervasive and invincible phenomenon inherent in human nature² are consistent with this understanding of mercenary arrangement of hierarchy in animal and human communities. That is why we should not overlook the hint given to us almost 2.5 thousand years ago by Aristotle, a great connoisseur of the organic world and creator of zoology, who thinking about man and his essence, saw this "work of nature" primarily as a "political animal" [2, p. 7]. First of all, he, certainly, gave recognition to the uniqueness of man focusing on the "political" notion, meaning a polis animal, i.e. living in ancient Greece in small hierarchical city-settlements and therefore capable of the highest form of communication, i.e. politics, providing, as he put it, a "good life" in people's coexistence. That said, Aristotle directly states that a person basically remains an animal [Gr. zoon politikon] and therefore his behavior is determined by the biological nature and primitive past.

In this regard, it is very indicative that, along with the unique "political aspect" and simultaneous "animal aspect" of human nature, it is precisely the criterion of corruption, i.e. "deterioration", "decay", "collapse" and "destruction" of the state (lat. "corruption" [13, p. 80]) allowed Aristotle to separate the so-called "right" forms of government from the "wrong" ones. In his opinion, the right ones (monarchy, aristocracy, polity) are those in which the public welfare, solidarity of fellow citizens and national benefit prevail. And he considered the state systems (tyranny, oligarchy, ochlocracy as an extreme form of democracy) in which those in power, first of all, pursue their selfish gain to the detriment of common interest, to be the wrong ones [1, p. 105, 124].

It is noteworthy that in the 70s of the 19th century M. Bakunin, Russian anarchist thinker, also justified the old age of corruption, relating it to the birth of the state. "There has never been a state," he stressed, "which would not have resorted to corruption as a means of control to any extent." Moreover, he saw corruption as a set of criminal acts, but following Machiavelli emphasized its ability to preserve and strengthen statehood and therefore acceptable thereto. "From that moment," the thinker insisted, "when crime begins to serve as an instrument of the state, it becomes virtuous" [5, p. 61, 64].

The eternal natural background of the connection between power as a product of hierarchical relations and biological individuals' (specimen's) tendencies

² Anti-Corruption Policy: Manual for Graduate Students Majoring in Management, Economics, Law, Social Studies, Political Science / Regional Public Foundation "Information

Science for Democracy" (INDEM Foundation); [G.A. Satarov et al.]; edited by G.A. Satarov. - Moscow: RA "SPAS", 2004, p. 190-191.

corresponding to these relations to appropriate someone else's goods in different ways is most clearly described in the works of domestic and foreign ethologists [7, p. 221-222; 8, p. 12-21; 9, p. 37-45; 16, p. 167-169]. With a bulk of factual evidence, they demonstrate that typical and diverse methods of appropriation and theft within hierarchical arrangement of primate communities, including higher primate communities, are not only specific forms of them "feeding" each other. Rank subordination of individuals simultaneously serves as a kind of "food chain", which, together with mutual feeding, structures and organizes their cooperative interaction. This, in turn, contributes to a better survival of individuals in their community, and to their effective protection from internal conflicts over food split-up and, therefore, unity in the face of external dangers and threats. Furthermore, relations of power and obedience thereto, including individual feeding forms corresponding to the ranks of individuals, more clearly organize reproductive relations between the sexes, thereby contributing to better reproduction and viable offspring [14, p. 84-88].

It should be emphasized that biologists and ethologists, following Aristotle, have no doubt today that being a "political animal", homo sapiens by his nature remains, in naturalist terms, a "hierarchical primate" [7, p. 227]. Basically, different concepts mean the same thing, since politics always implies a race for power and an appropriate rank in the animal and human hierarchy [7, p. 249-253]. Therefore, it is not unreasonable to assume that innate behavior programs coming with man's evolution and his subordination relations remained in place in herd hierarchies. Subtly, contributing to society's organization and controllability, they manifest themselves in a hierarchically integrated to this day human community.

Therefore, it is quite possible that their ineradicability is clearly manifested, in particular, in the so-called "illegal", i.e. without prior permission and "semi-official" corruption, which is based on administrative markup and is typical for authoritarian and patriarchal political regimes [21, p. 467; 3, p. 19]. It is still an instrument of vertical control in the bureaucratic hierarchy in some post-Soviet, Latin American and African countries. Providing officials with extra income and "in-office feeding", such corruption improves their obedience and loyalty to management, official duty performance and respect for rank. This is due to the unlawfulness and illegitimacy of their shadow corruption profits and hence increasing vulnerability of their recipients, fear of falling under the pressure of public outrage, or out of favor with their management and ending up behind bars [18, p. 146-149]. In a word, to understand whether there is a biological component in various forms of corrupt behavior, it is necessary to look more closely at natural and human algorithms of selfish manipulation of power, generally used to the detriment of humanization and social development.

As for hominids, human ancestors, stable hierarchy, subordination of individuals in various groups - a herd, family, depending on their physical strength and skill, age, sex, aggressiveness (persistence and preda-

tion), combined with episodic egalitarianism, have prevailed in the organization of communities for hundreds of thousands and millions of years. The presence of a group of hierarchical instincts in a person is confirmed not only by the parallel development of the same subordination programs in his closest relatives, for example, chimpanzees or baboons and gorillas. That said, it is very important that alongside these ancestral algorithms and convergently, that is, under similar conditions and for similar purposes, peoples' relatives among primates and our direct ancestors developed the same adaptive programs of behavior in the herd. Although, their genetic basis may be different.

So, vertically integrated primates' and peoples' communities have had dominants ("leaders", "chiefs", "politicians", "authorities", "alpha males") at the top, followed by subdominants ("ruling groups", "elite") with "ordinary people", "plebs", "common folks", "rabble", "thieves" (meaning humble origin), who can not only be controlled, but also pushed around, living at the bottom. At the same time, males in a herd of social primates most often and all their lives compete for a high rank in the hierarchy. It allows for influencing not only the balance of power in the community ("chimpanzee politics"), but also having the most delicious food, attractive and fertile females, and places convenient for everyday living. In a word, power, as a structural component of the relations of domination and obedience was and, for the most part, remains a manifestation of the laws of the existence of hierarchies, and not only in the animal, but also in the primitive human world by virtue of evolution. The agricultural revolution (10 thousand years B.C.) and development of agriculture, which products had not only to be preserved, but also accumulated and distributed, contributed to the growth of hierarchy's predominance. "Rulers and elites entered the picture throughout the world and swallowed up food stocks accumulated by farmers, leaving the poor with only slender food" [20, p. 123].

Thus, with a set of instinctive hierarchical behavior programs perfected by millions of years of group survival and natural selection, people entered into property, social and political relations among themselves. It should be kept in mind that the human brain is designed so that its part responsible for consciousness cannot get acquainted with the content of many instinctive programs. And besides, they "sleep" for the time being, however, are ready for actualization on occasion. Meanwhile, a man predominantly explains and rationalizes his behavior in society as a result of his rational activity. And wishing or not, peoples' minds provide only the spontaneous implementation of innate algorithms of their behavioral activity. Besides, for that reason, it often finds illusory, only imaginary explanations for the drives and motives for human being's actions. Certainly, consciousness is able to recognize, in particular, food, sex and defense instincts, control them, directing them in a socially acceptable direction. But the more complex innate components of human social behavior and psyche largely remain outside of his mental reflection. For example, the tendency to ethologically isolate species that has evolved is already difficult to identify intellectually, although it may be behind such

dangerous phenomena as racism, aggressive nationalism, or nepotism, for example, in the distribution of various vital resources by power holders among their own people and relatives [19, p. 397-407].

In this regard, it is noteworthy that primates, including higher ones, have a widespread instinctive program of taking away various goods from their conspecifics in the lower levels of the animal hierarchy. In this case, it takes effect without the use of force, various benefits are obtained, so to speak, "by rank", that is, by the right of rank superiority and dominance [9, p. 38]. For example, among social monkeys, subordinate specimens tend to obediently and meekly give away their valuables - tidbits of food, entertaining toys, attractive females, which aroused a keen interest in the dominant or alpha male. It should be emphasized that this method of "misappropriation" not only compels to transfer benefits top-down, but also strengthens hierarchical subordination of specimen necessary in organizing their group life.

It seems that this ancestral program has a historically nature-like equivalent in human custom to present various "gifts" to officials in the hope of their patronage and favor. It may be recalled that primitive societies had a custom to bring regular offerings to leaders and priests to ensure their affection. And the ancestors of the Slavs, for instance, in their pagan rituals covered the earth god's mouth and lips on his wooden image with honey in order to please him. Isn't that why an old saying about catering to those who have power - "you need to grease some palms" was born later?! In any case, such rooted customs as "feeding" military leaders, government officials and judges, the population "bringing" various food and utensils to these servicemen, the rules of the so-called "honors", "promises" and bakshesh given to bureaucracy and in order to facilitate resolution of particular problems of ordinary petitioners have been long known in Russia [11, p. 15-16]. At first, all these voluntary and also forced gifts were not considered as bribes. In a word, it is obvious that a whole subculture of offerings, gifts, donations stimulating self-serving relations between bosses and ordinary people has grown through an innate biological program. At the same time, it consolidated their specific reciprocity, hierarchical and stable coherence, their rank subordination in Russia's autocratic statehood. Because of the poverty of the Old Russian state, by Byzantine tradition, its maintenance was entirely laid upon the population living in the territory entrusted to sent or local officials. Therefore, in the 11th century, the instinctive conditionality of relations between the bureaucracy and the inhabitants was codified in *Russkaya Pravda*, the first collection of legal acts. Prince Yaroslav the Wise made it clear there that ordinary people are responsible for supporting their governors, imposing severe penalties for failure to comply with this command [3, p. 19].

And today, some representatives of Russian bureaucracy quite bluntly use the "gifts" and offerings of their benefactors in everyday life. Every once in a while dignitaries show off watches worth thousands, or even tens of thousands of dollars, put on trendy clothes of expensive world brands, speed around in luxury cars and yachts, live in penthouses and palace complexes,

paid by industrial oligarchs and rich do-gooders. Some of the state administrative elite, secretly having dual citizenship, residence permits in other countries, passports with multi-year visas, covertly acquire luxurious real estate in Europe and the USA, open accounts in Zurich and London through figureheads, educate their children at Oxford and Harvard, takes a "well-earned" rest on the Cote d'Azur. It is highly unlikely that all these premium-class benefits can be honestly earned even by hard years of work in Russian state or municipal service.

Another ancestral program of appropriating behavior, repeatedly described by ethologists and similar to human actions, is the take-over and retention of the very source of vital goods. Animals primarily favor food-rich areas, water resources, fruit-bearing trees and plants, edible carcasses and herds of sedentary animals as a hunting prey. As a rule, the strongest and the most aggressive take possession of this good, as they can do away with all other challengers. Examples, when the hunk of bread is taken over from geese or a feeder from tits and pigeons by the most perky and pushy, are legion. Other species have more sophisticated ways of taking possession of the source of riches: in a wolf pack, this is no longer done alone, but in a group. And if fertile sources in nature can be normally taken over by the most clever, feline and strong specimen, for their conspecifics the very fact of possessing them is evidence of the "legitimacy" of their power and authority in an animal community [10, p. 23].

In humans, such a program manifests itself already in early childhood - in juvenile hassles for kindergarten toys, in the struggle for the right to control local territories, in city gates and on village streets. However, already adult individuals vested with power, break bad and appropriate public assets by any means possible - fertile hectares of land, profitable enterprises at the privatization stage, large budget funds, rental income from the export of oil, gas, timber, metals, fish and other mineral wealth. That said, superiors sometimes try to control someone else's business in such a way as to ensure a regular profit for providing tax breaks, various property benefits, and a monopoly in obtaining state and municipal orders.

This criminal subculture also offers "seizure", "purchase" of senior posts in governing bodies that have the power to distribute valuable material resources. Appropriation and usurpation to enrich the public power tops - the official positions of senior officials in ministries and central departments, in supervisory, law enforcement, judicial and information systems, is most destructive for society. Then these "fruitful", corruptogenic posts turn into an abundant money-making source for political rings and clans, other dominant groups that form the cobwebs of corruption networks and manage society for their own benefits. And if that is the case, such a state may suffer degradation and collapse in the long run. No wonder that the word "corruption" in ancient Greek has this last meaning - "destruction" of something [13, p. 80].

Many social animals, higher primates surely included, have another simple program of taking away food or other good through violence. Often, cubs start

to rob their peers earlier than communicate and establish useful contacts with them. And in adulthood, taking possession of other specimen's goods already happens not only thanks to violence, but also using specimen's dominant rank. This is occasionally done, for example, symbolically by herd monkeys: a tidbit is given to a specimen of lower rank, and taken away immediately. And the procedure is repeated several times in a row: give-take away. This gives a signal to subordinate specimen about hierarchical superiority and the need to strengthen their submission in the herd by unconditional obedience [9, p. 39].

Obviously, this program of social animals' behavior in their hierarchies is very similar to bureaucratic pressure, which creates coercion to offerings, kick-backs, illegal "contributions" and payments by citizens in exchange for official actions or wrongful omissions by bureaucrats. It's clever to build such requirements for solvent and wealthy people so that they can meekly tolerate this "rip-off" and, reluctantly, acknowledge and tolerate their management's high "managerial" art of working with public and business authorities. This "managerial skill" clearly strengthens the vertical hierarchy in society.

It should be kept in mind though that frank robbery of subordinates by rank and status among social animals is balanced by another innate way of obtaining others' goods - their secret stealing. As stressed by ethologists, this stealing is fundamentally different from "superiors" robbery and coercion to offerings in that it is committed by inferiors to those being robbed [9, p. 38]. That is why it is done secretly using various tricks. And having skillfully sneaked, subordinate animals run away and hide the stolen, or secretly devour edibles. It should be stressed that the more rigid the hierarchical organization of the herd, the stronger, for example, among social monkeys, the theft. Therefore, it is surely empirically reliable to think here that in a stable ratio of "superiors" robbery, on the one hand, and secret looting by subordinates of their dominants, on the other hand, relations of domination and obedience in the herd are eventually strengthened and balanced.

It is apparent that such higher primates as homo sapiens have a similar "food chain" in various hierarchies. The combination of stealing and embezzlement is evident when the bureaucracy has access to leadership opportunities allowing for self-serving distribution of state revenues and public resources through various sophisticated tricks. Embezzlement of public funds, fraud, misappropriation and embezzlement of budget funds, or, for example, servants stealing various values belonging to wealthy owners in everyday life is a typical picture of a great variety of crimes and offenses in various socio-political hierarchies. Therefore it is not surprising that, for example, the Demidovs, famous Ural industrialists, allowed managers of their factories and households to secretly steal up to 10 percent of proprietary income. They believed this extra income to the official pay of their "effective managers" to be inevitable and therefore did not punish for it.

The evolutionary program of animal behavior such as fraudulent exchange is explanatory in the con-

text of misappropriation. For example, ravens and monkeys, who have a natural aptitude for cunning and the ability to fool a partner, slip a sham instead of the right thing, or grab valuable items they seem to exchange, have a high level of it. Needless to say that the sapiens also has quite a high level of fraudulent exchange, since he is also often driven by a latent desire to play a trick on a partner and thereby get his profits. Honesty and like-kind exchange are quite late achievements obtained by reason and culture. They partially neutralize these "400 relatively honest ways of taking off goods" (named after Ostap Bender), cultivated by the most cunning and arrogant individuals, in high places too, for their survival. In a word, the subconscious fraudulent program remains in place and quite often asserts itself in full in criminal and administrative offenses.

Thus, for example, fraud by persons in charge thrives in organizing tenders for central and local government procurement secured by large budget funds. Measures taken by the legislators that have consistently toughened the requirements for tenders in new laws and regulations and tightened sanctions for their violation have not yet nullified these sophisticated and criminal arts and tricks. The damage caused by public procurement fraud by officials, especially in the military and industrial and space sectors involving huge public funds, is sometimes measured in astronomic sums of money.

Animals have several other kleptocratic programs that contribute to the strengthening and relatively successful functioning of the "managerial" power vertical in their communities. Similar programs can be easily found among the list of abuse of power by power holders in human society.

Biologists are well aware that struggle for hierarchical rank is an important part of herd dog-headed monkeys' (savanna baboons, baboons, hamadryas baboons) life. The dominant position allows those who have achieved it not only to derive more pleasure from tidbits and attractive sexual partners, but also provides better offspring survival and reproductive success. Meanwhile, the lower ranked individuals, especially those at the bottom of the pyramid ("scum"), are chronically stressed, are more likely to have fears and panic attacks, get sick worse and live less as a result. However, being rather pressed by dominants, they mastered the "craft" of persistent begging, which mitigates the pressure from the power vertical and makes their life more bearable. According to ethologists, animals use their skills to beg for something useful with respect to those who are stronger, more successful and higher in rank and can share something valuable [9, p. 39].

It's worth noting that humans have a higher begging level than other animals. We are constantly asking, pleading, begging, bowing, calling for, soliciting, praying to the Almighty, imploring, demanding, pleasing, etc. However, in the bureaucratic class, this inherently innate tendency has clearly become a corrupt art, including sophisticated begging and pesky requests addressed to wealthy citizens and prosperous enterprises. Officials enthusiastically create say various extrabudgetary, social and charitable funds, which, however, primarily serve their own needs and mercenary interests.

Now and then they are busy building such administrative barriers hindering the creation, registration and strengthening of private firms and enterprises and confuse businessmen who are forced to pay a bribe to overcome them. It can be believed that animal begging and extortion skills remained in place, which only blossomed, became civilized and often serve to feed the gluttonous bureaucratic tribe in relationship with the wealthy and the rich.

Speaking of, the lower classes soliciting help and begging organically fits in the hierarchical chain with the dominants tending to endow their subordinates, sometimes exceptionally catering thereto. However, as observed by scientists, herd monkey hierarchs, for example, are not eager to give away what they have gained by their own efforts to others. But they “generously” give away those riches they have managed to take away from someone, but cannot use themselves or hide because of nomad existence or otherwise. Therefore, dominants often use “surpluses” to demonstrate and strengthen their rank superiority. In a word, the bones thrown by the hierarchs to their tribesmen are not so much charity and “humanitarian aid” as the implementation of an innate population program to strengthen the vertical integration of members of this community [9, p. 39].

It is hardly possible to deny such cause of peoples’ actions when wielding political or administrative power. No wonder that Frans de Waal, a prominent American primatologist, insists that “humans are hierarchical primates no matter how hard we try to camouflage the fact ...” [6, p. 306]. And, of course, this literally outstanding primate primarily favors “his own”, “socially close” people - members of his family, clan, ethnic group, class and religion, political party or fellow countrymen and classmates. He often does this not only to help them settle in life. Such corruption phenomena as nepotism, favoritism and protectionism open up other sides of motivation for his good deeds. Most likely, hierarchical tendencies also give rise to the desire to organize such coalitions and client groups that would occasionally be capable of supporting his rank positions, authority and privileges. Therefore, it is hardly worth denying that peoples’ patronizing actions have elements of their innate craving for power and influence.

The convergency of self-serving power manipulations by human individuals that we have demonstrated and which integrates them within the context of the natural life of their related creatures, allows us to draw some conclusions useful for developing comprehensive anti-corruption measures.

Firstly, the assumptions that corruption crimes and offenses originate and are somewhat enabled by specific instinctive behavior programs of higher primates (and other animals) in relations of domination and obedience among themselves, are quite reasonable and have extensive factual background. At the same time,

hominids’, human relatives, skills to appropriate someone else’s property - take away, rob, steal the goods that do not belong to them, are quite neutral, if not practically useful in terms of evaluation. After all, the chain of mutual feeding originating with a combination of these catches (for example, the dominant taking away forcefully and his subordinate begging), ultimately turns into a coherent rank ratio and hierarchical organization of animal community. At the same time, it should be stressed that this subordination is not developed once and for all, it changes with the rank of those who have power. Therefore, it is generally supported, somewhat stabilized and rooted in the herd by the “food chain” functioning thanks to mutual feeding methods. In turn, the hierarchy makes populations and communities structured, allows dampening down destructive controversies between individuals during food split-up, arranging herd protection from external threats, and overcoming various misfortunes in course of group survival. Moreover, hierarchical relationships contribute to the reproduction of viable offspring from the strongest and most persistent organisms in sexual selection.

Of course, it’s hard for a person to accept this typically “immoral” hierarchy in nature, since similar actions taken by people are often directly embodied in the elements of crime and suffer social ostracism. However, dominant groups in human society, especially in authoritarian and dictatorial regimes, do resort to kleptocratic methods of strengthening their dominance and seek to control society on their basis. And then it becomes quite obvious that the methods of appropriation of others’ goods in nature correlate with and are similar to the body of offences by corrupt officials.

Secondly, we can believe that animal roots of corruption show in manic greed and ardent money-grubbing - these secret passions officials have for wealth accumulation, their drug intoxication from corruption opportunities authorities have. Having dug into wrongdoing, these representatives of the ruling class can rarely stop. Of course, the magic of the power itself, capable of providing its holders with financial wellbeing nearly in the blink of an eye is also relevant for their “insanity”. Money or jewelry appropriated with its help miraculously increase by a wide margin and can be measured in tens and even hundreds of kilograms. And land, for instance - in thousands of hectares³.

Thus, the natural “criminal” heritage manifests itself in the severe obsession of corrupt officials who boldly misappropriate large property and hefty sums of money against any prudence and the risk of being caught with their hands in the till. It is also important to bear in mind that if an ordinary citizen needs most of his life to acquire his own comfortable housing, land allotment, modern vehicle, with the magic of power a person can get much more in no time. That is why not everyone can resist the demonic temptation to quickly get rich and release from captivity of everyday needs.

³ Let us recall once again Aleksandr Menshikov, an associate of Peter the Great, whose wealth exceeded the annual budget of the Russian Empire. Or the present former officials Vasilieva (Ministry of Defense), Khoroshavin (ex-governor of Sakhalin) and Zakharchenko (colonel of the Ministry of

Internal Affairs), whose jewelry and banknotes seized by the Investigative Committee of the Russian Federation weighed hundreds of kilograms and were exported from safe houses by trucks.

Thirdly, it appears that the ancestral roots of theft, robbery and taking away of wealth by those in power manifest themselves in a wide-scale, sometimes overwhelming corruption, its pervasive property to be present in the main areas of administrative authorities' expertise. Having disappeared as a result of effective anti-corruption measures in one area, this kleptocratic fondness, revived by the presence of superiority and domination, immediately and spontaneously manifests itself in another. In a word, because of a group of hierarchical instincts that sometimes latently focuses their carriers on power and money-making, corruption is not only a systemic, but also a cornerstone phenomenon, regularly reviving in various areas of ruling groups. In this regard, it resembles decay, damage and rust affecting any bodies and things over time. It also leads to degradation, decline and destruction of even initially healthy social relations, which, like everything in the world, require efforts to have them maintained, "decontaminated" and renewed.

Let us emphasize that natural programs of social behavior are merely unconscious, as when wielding power or resigning thereto, a man is not normally aware of innate motivation. He believes that he is acting as he sees fit, that he is used to it and needs it. However, this does not mean that sapiens is a "blind slave" of his instincts and there is an animal born inside him that turns him into a primitive primate. As known from evolutionary biology, there are many gap fillers between hereditary programs recorded in gene combinations and actual behavioral acts. From protein coding (done by genes themselves) to electrochemical and neurophysiological processes, which, in turn, are influenced by the culture and psychology of a particular individual. That is why innate biological programs and corresponding emotions involving certain values (commitment to justice, for example) normally do not dictate us to do anything. Biological programs make it out only to our desires, but not their indispensable implementation. They gently, "whispering", so to speak, guide us, encouraging certain actions. It seems that an evolutionary program manifests itself only in a persistent tendency to act in a particular way, and not otherwise, to follow a certain path. It should also not be forgotten that here human consciousness only caters to natural desires, as it does, say, when choosing a sexual partner, striving to satisfy hunger, thirst, or in a persistent tendency to help his offspring by virtue of parental instincts inherent in most animals including humans.

That said, the human has a certain freedom of action allowing for meaningful choice, contingent on his morality, culture, development of intelligence and self-awareness. That is why when dominating over or submitting to other people, a person is only prone to and risks unblocking, awakening certain instincts in himself. And becoming a creature relevant to his relic nature - a reckless and thieving representative of the higher primates population, that is, "run wild" again for a while. There are tons of examples of such reincarnation of people in power.

Therefore, it is obvious that specific instincts to appropriate someone else's goods cannot be rooted out by limiting authorities' actions with laws and ethical

standards, invoking their consciousness and conscience or raising their allowances. Moreover, growing scale and sophistication of embezzlement by those wielding power may only be aggravated by establishing new benefits and privileges aiming to lower their rent-seeking drive. This scenario increases the risk of them confusing state, public and personal pockets as when solving acute social problems and implementing reforms, the ruling class in Russia is always seeking to appropriate the right to determine its own support (that is, "feeding") by its population. The transformation of Russia's social structure throughout its history is largely associated with the redistribution of its national wealth.

It is also not enough, although crucial, to create and actively implement oversight procedures with respect to government apparatus by civil society institutions and coalitions. Thereby, the legal asymmetry of two key parties to the society - between state bodies with their monopoly on resort to force and civil society with its right to control application of this force without abuse of power, will be gradually eliminated.

It is equally important to systematically shape an anti-corruption mindset among central and local government officials and the country's population through educational organizations, the media and the Internet. Then in the future it can translate into appropriate habits and skills of everyday interaction between ordinary citizens and authorities. At the same time, many countries' experience indicates that these social measures produce only a partial, sometimes only a palliative effect, which does not affect the roots of corruption ramified in homo sapiens' nature. It is clear that when choosing personal options for exercising power, officials performing public administration functions should be aware at the back of their minds of the risks and price of losses - freedom, property, reputation, high retirement benefit, family well-being if they commit corruption crimes. Indeed, in contrast to crimes of passion such as violence or murder, when the subject often does not think about punishment at all, people involved in corrupt practices usually know the laws they violate and cover-up their actions. That is why such a strong natural instinct as fear and deterrence measures respectively are a strong factor in suppressing the rampant corruption and curbing the destructive human tendencies caused by the "demonic energy" of power. As they say, some innate and destructive passions must be opposed by equally strong other ones, capable of eliminating human thuggish behavior caused by animal vices.

Otherwise, politicians and officials who have a privileged social status and a dominant position compared with ordinary citizens, not fearing the inevitability and severity of punishment, sometimes perceive corruption opportunities as their original privileges for implementing personal profitable projects using power. They believe their implementation to be a low-risk and super-profitable activity that magically improves their personal finances. However, deep inside they explain these sometimes unjust and illegal acts by the fact that there are comparable profitable positions in real economy with corresponding benefits, which they are also entitled to when addressing important social causes. In

this case, it is appropriate to recall the famous thought of L.N. Tolstoy that “conscience of the privileged is a privileged conscience”.

Given the innate nature of many natural programs of behavior in power, their fundamental inevitability, it is important to eliminate, where possible, the very possibility of corruption. So, laws adopted without sufficient expertise sometimes have many loopholes for officials’ self-serving liberty. Therefore, qualified anti-corruption expertise and civil legal supervision over draft regulations should also become mandatory in everyday legislative process. Furthermore, the elimination of closed business contacts between officials and the public, politicians and businessmen, replacing them with web-based public service platforms, “virtual government”, “e-democracy” will also help to overcome corruption. Regular restaffing on top echelons of power in politics, central and local government, rotation and turnover of persons in charge in positions with high corruption risks are also very important. These important measures among democratic procedures will oppose the emergence of hierarchical kleptocratic programs in the actions of those who have power.

Therefore, deference and reduced opportunities for abuse of power, every kind of promotion of honesty and integrity in the actions of those vested with it are the basic factors lowering the risks of corruption, its functioning and expansion. Unless this is done, the web of discretions to powers and authority and instinctive programs for their exercise can manifest itself in the most unexpected and destructive way for society.

That said, it should be emphasized that corruption exists not only because the relic nature of homo sapiens is imperfect, so that a comprehensive anti-corruption policy embodying combined efforts of the state and civil society involves many other useful measures and procedures.

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